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GENDER INEQUALITY ISSUES

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KATA SAMBUTAN

Puji syukur kehadirat Tuhan Yang Maha Esa, akhirnya kami dapat menerbitkan **OUTLOOK JAPAN: *Journal of Japanese Area Studies*** Vol. 10 No. 2 edisi bulan Desember 2022. Kami sampaikan penghargaan yang setinggi-tingginya dan terima kasih yang sebesar-besarnya kepada para penyumbang artikel, tim redaksi yang telah bekerja keras mengumpulkan, mengedit naskah, sampai dengan proses penerbitan. Tak kalah pentingnya, terimakasih sedalam-dalamnya kepada The Japan Foundation Jakarta yang senantiasa memberikan sumbangsih dana atas jurnal yang dikelola oleh Asosiasi Studi Jepang di Indonesia (ASJI), sehingga kami bisa secara konsisten menerbitkan jurnal ini pada setiap tahunnya.

Jurnal **OUTLOOK JAPAN: *Journal of Japanese Area Studies*** menyajikan artikel-artikel yang berkaitan dengan studi Jepang dari berbagai sudut pandang keilmuan. Dalam edisi jurnal kali ini dimuat beberapa artikel dengan isu sosial politik, ekonomi dan budaya terkait masalah perempuan. Diharapkan artikel yang termuat dalam jurnal kali ini dapat menjadi referensi yang bermanfaat bagi para pengaji studi Jepang sehingga dapat memahami Jepang lebih mendalam lagi, khususnya yang terkait dengan nilai sosial - budaya dan falsafah hidup orang Jepang.

Jurnal ini juga dapat menjadi wadah publikasi hasil penelitian bagi para peneliti keJepangan, selain juga dapat dijadikan media pertukaran informasi yang dapat meningkatkan kualitas akademik para pengajar, pembelajar dan para pemerhati keJepangan. Hal itu pada akhirnya akan berguna bagi pengembangan studi keJepangan di Indonesia baik pada saat ini maupun pada masa yang akan datang.

Untuk menjaga kesinambungan jurnal ini kami mengharapkan dukungan semua pihak yang berkecimpung dalam bidang studi Jepang, terutama para anggota Asosiasi Studi Jepang di Indonesia (ASJI), sekiranya dapat aktif menyumbangkan naskah atau artikel untuk edisi jurnal selanjutnya.

Editor in Chief

KATA PENGANTAR

OUTLOOK JAPAN: *Journal of Japanese Area Studies* Volume 10 No. 2 edisi Desember 2022 mengangkat tema ***Gender Inequality Issues***. Subjeknya adalah tentang gender, yaitu mengkaji mengenai perempuan dari kacamata emansipasi yang universal dengan menggunakan isu pemberdayaan perempuan sebagai kebudayaan residu atau masal yang mengarah pada bentuk kebudayaan dari kelompok yang mengalami tekanan. Teori dan metode yang disajikan terkait masalah ketidaksetaraan gender baik di Jepang maupun Indonesia dapat dikaji berdasarkan perspektif kritis dengan tujuan memajukan sebuah sintesa dan pertimbangan umum yang terjadi di masyarakat.

Melalui riset yang dilakukan para peneliti yang tertuang dalam artikel atau naskah di jurnal ini telah memperluas pengertian kita tentang berbagai isu terkait dengan perempuan yang mana dikaji dari berbagai perspektif. Hal ini memberi sumbangan bagi pendefinisian yang lebih jelas dan pengetahuan yang lebih baik terkait bidang sosial-budaya, politik dan ekonomi, sebagaimana tertuang dalam artikel di jurnal ini antara lain : “*Perempuan Jepang: Quo Vadis*”; “*Perempuan Dalam Karya-Karya Murakami Haruki*” dan “*Gender Inequality in Japan: Critical Perspectives and The Explanation of Five Elements of Social Problems by Rubington and Weinberg.*”

Melalui artikel atau naskah yang termuat dalam jurnal Volume 10 No. 2 edisi Desember 2022 ini diharapkan pembaca dapat memahami isi dari artikel yang ada dan menambah wawasan untuk mengenal lebih dalam budaya, nilai-nilai serta norma-norma suatu bangsa.

Editor

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STUDENT PERCEPTIONS OF GENDER EQUALITY VALUE: A CASE STUDY OF JAPANESE LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE UNIVERSITY STUDENT ORGANIZATIONS IN MEDAN

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ABSTRACT

Kesetaraan gender masih menjadi isu umum yang diamati dalam berbagai aspek kehidupan, dan fenomena tersebut dapat dikategorikan berdasarkan kelompok dan kelas sosial. Adapun fenomena yang dilatarbelakangi oleh persepsi gender di kalangan pemuda dan mahasiswa dengan aktivitas organisasi internal kampus yang beragam. Penelitian ini mengkaji persepsi mahasiswa program bahasa dan sastra Jepang di Medan tentang kesetaraan gender dalam kegiatan organisasi. Penelitian ini menggunakan metodologi kualitatif dan disajikan secara deskriptif. Observasi dan wawancara dilakukan kepada anggota organisasi mahasiswa program bahasa dan sastra Jepang di Medan. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa persepsi siswa tentang kesetaraan gender masih rendah. Secara hukum, mahasiswa telah menerima aturan tertulis organisasi, tetapi bias gender masih terlihat dalam praktik organisasi. Hal ini dibuktikan dengan laki-laki menduduki manajemen dan kepengurusan organisasi di ranah publik, sedangkan perempuan hanya menduduki jabatan manajemen di ranah domestik. Fenomena ini berlangsung cukup lama, menanamkan rasa rendah diri pada anggota perempuan di setiap organisasi mahasiswa program bahasa dan sastra Jepang di Medan.

Keywords: *Kesetaraan gender, Organisasi kemahasiswaan, Mahasiswa Bahasa dan Sastra Jepang, Medan*

INTRODUCTION

Gender issues remain a highly significant and relevant in various aspects of society, including among students. These gender issues pertain to the differences in treatment and opportunities between men and women in the majority of countries worldwide. While numerous efforts have been undertaken to raise awareness about these issues, the reality remains that gender discrimination is still widespread.

Among students, gender issues often manifest as gender bias within student organizations (Lestari, 2016). This bias can impact stereotypes of women who are only suitable for domestic roles and less capable in public roles (Kurniawan & Mulyani, 2018). This is undoubtedly detrimental to women who wish to participate in these organizations actively. Furthermore, gender bias can create a sense of superiority and inferiority among organization members (Nwangwu & Ezeibe, 2019; Slavik, 2007).

The concepts of gender and sex are distinct but often mistakenly regarded as the same thing (Kartini & Maulana, 2019; Kawashima, 1999; Taulia, 2016). Gender refers to the social roles, behaviours, and identities considered appropriate for men or women in a given society. In contrast, sex entails the biological characteristics that differentiate males and females, such as genital organs and chromosomes. Literature students in Medan have a fairly good understanding of the differences between gender and sex, as these topics are covered in literature and macro-linguistic courses such as sociolinguistics. Unfortunately, there is still a lack of awareness of the importance of promoting gender equality in their environment. One concrete example is the persistence of gender bias within groups where students actualise their social roles (Simorangkir & Andayani, 2021), namely student organizations or *Himpunan Mahasiswa Jurusan* (HMJ).

Gender bias can create damaging and inaccurate stereotypes of women (Eizmendi-Iraola & Peña-Fernández, 2022; Lin et al., 2023; Rahminawati, 2021). Such stereotypes often depict women as only suitable for domestic roles within organizations, such as managing consumption-related tasks and correspondence. Men are seen as more suited for public positions, like leading meetings, giving speeches, or serving as chairpersons. This is undoubtedly detrimental and diminishes the role of women, as they are frequently underestimated or perceived as less capable in various fields when, in reality, this is not the case.

The perpetuation of this phenomenon over an extended period can also lead to a state of superiority and inferiority between men and women within student organizations. In many cases, men are considered superior to women, resulting in women often not having equal opportunities in various aspects. This disparity becomes even more evident in student organizations, where a gap exists between men's and women's treatment.

The phenomenon and reality of gender equality among Japanese literature students in organizational activities are extremely relevant and important to discuss. Japanese literature students at the Universitas Sumatera Utara must understand gender rights and advocate for comprehensive gender equality, including in organizational activities.

The role of student organizations is crucial in fostering awareness of gender issues. Organizations must actively work toward promoting gender equality, eliminating gender stereotypes and biases, and creating an inclusive environment that embraces all individuals without discrimination. Students should also be able to appreciate individual differences by evaluating someone's abilities, skills, and contributions within the organization. Thus, this writing will serve as an introduction to a study discussing gender equality among students, starting with the student's perceptions of gender equality within the scope of Japanese literature student organizations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Gender Bias

Gender bias refers to the negative or positive views or attitudes toward an individual based on sex. This bias occurs because society tends to perceive men and women differently, particularly in terms of characteristics, behaviours, abilities, and roles appropriate to their gender (Adams et al., 2022; Setyaningsih et al., 2019; Sigurdardottir et al., 2023).

A study conducted by Accademia Europea in Italy demonstrates that gender bias can influence employee selection processes, wherein male applicants are more often chosen over female applicants despite having similar qualifications and work experience. This is due to stereotypes that certain jobs are more suitable for men or women, leading

companies to prefer candidates who conform to the perceived appropriate gender (Moss-Racusin et al., 2012; Reuben et al., 2014).

Stereotypes associated with gender bias can cause women to feel less confident and undervalued in the workplace and in everyday life. A study by KPMG found that 55% of women felt undervalued in their jobs, while only 35% of men felt the same way. This indicates a gap in treatment between men and women that still exists in society (KPMG, 2015).

Unfortunately, gender bias is not only present in the workplace but also in educational environments. Research by UNESCO shows that gender bias in curricula can influence students' views and attitudes towards males and females. This can lead children, both boys and girls, to have inaccurate views about the abilities and characteristics of the opposite sex (Bromley & Willis, 2015; UNESCO, 2018).

To address gender bias, concrete actions are needed from various parties such as families, schools, communities, and governments. Schools and educational institutions should eliminate discriminatory curricula and teach gender equality values from an early age. Governments should also provide pro-gender equality policies and encourage the creation of inclusive environments that embrace all individuals without discrimination. By doing so, it is hoped that it can help reduce or even eliminate gender bias gradually in society.

Public and Domestic Role Stereotypes

The stereotype of public and domestic roles is a common perception attached to men and women in society. This stereotype states that women should be better at doing household chores and caring for children, while men should take on public roles such as working in an office or leading an organization (Junaidi, 2017; Lin et al., 2023).

A study by the American Psychological Association shows that stereotypes of public and domestic roles can affect individual behaviour and aspirations (Yasrial, 2018). Women exposed to domestic role stereotypes tend to have less ambitious careers than men (Ismiati, 2018). In addition, women who work in technology tend to feel uncomfortable because men dominate the work environment.

One of the recent studies on stereotypes was conducted by the American Sociological Association and published in 2021. The study shows that stereotypes of public and domestic roles are still very much

attached to society today, despite increased awareness of the importance of gender equality (Tilcsik, 2021).

The study involved more than 4,500 adult respondents in the United States and found that most respondents still hold traditional views about the roles of men and women in the household and the workplace. As many as 57% of respondents believe that women's main job is to take care of children and the family, while only 13% believe that women's main job is to work outside the home (Kim Parker et al., 2017).

The study also found that stereotypes of public and domestic roles can impact individuals' careers and income. Women who focus on household and family tasks tend to have lower incomes than men or women who pursue careers outside the home.

The study concludes that stereotypes of public and domestic roles continue to hinder achieving gender equality overall. Therefore, greater efforts are needed from various parties to eliminate these stereotypes and create an inclusive environment that embraces all individuals without discrimination.

Another study conducted in India shows that stereotypes of public and domestic roles also affect family decision-making about children's education. Families with traditional views are more likely to send their sons to school and involve them in extracurricular activities to improve leadership skills, while daughters are asked to help with household chores and are evaluated based on their cooking or craft skills (Kingdon, 2005; LexQuest, 2018).

Stereotypes of public and domestic roles can also affect student organization activities on campus. For example, there is a tendency for important positions in organizations, such as chairman or coordinator, to be given to men because they are considered more suitable and capable of leading organizations.

This results in a gap in treatment between men and women in student organizations. Women are often underestimated or considered less capable in various fields, even though it is untrue. Stereotypes of public and domestic roles also make women feel uncomfortable and unsafe taking risks in the running for positions considered "masculine".

Inferiority and Superiority

Women's inferiority and men's superiority are patriarchal cultural views that state that men are inherently superior to women

(Adawiyah & Hasanah, 2020; Setiawan & Darni, 2022). This view can be found in various aspects of life, such as work, leadership, and academic achievement.

A study by the American Psychological Association shows that the inferiority of women and the superiority of men can affect individuals' perceptions of their capabilities. Women tend to feel less confident and underestimate their abilities, while men tend to feel more confident and overestimate their abilities.

The results of a survey conducted in 2021 and published by the Pew Research Center show that views of the inferiority of women and the superiority of men still exist in society today. As many as 53% of respondents believe that men are better than women in political leadership, while only 7% believe otherwise. In addition, around 40% of respondents believe that men are better in business and finance, while only 5% believe that women are better in these fields (K Parker et al., 2018).

METHOD

The research method that can be used to explore the views of Japanese literature students regarding gender roles in the student organization of the Japanese Literature Student Association in Medan is qualitative research that utilises open interviews and document studies as data sources (Gunawan, 2015; Moleong, 2014).

This qualitative research will be conducted through open interviews with Japanese literature students at Universitas Sumatera Utara who are student organization members, such as *Aotake* and *Hinode*, and the Japanese Language Student Association at Universitas Harapan Medan called *Hikari*. These three organizations were chosen because they are Medan's only Japanese language and literature study programs. In addition, document studies will be used as secondary data to explore students' views on gender roles in organizations.

The first step in this study is to determine the population and sample of the research. The target population is Japanese literature and language students in Medan who are members of the Japanese Literature and Language Student Association, namely *Aotake*, *Hinode*, and *Hikari*. The research sample was selected through purposive sampling by considering specific characteristics such as gender, age, and

organizational experience. The researcher chose respondents who were considered to represent diversity in the organization and had sufficient experience, including core officials, chairpersons, secretaries, and treasurers, as well as several coordinators in each field and one member in each coordinator's area, with a total of 15 respondents. Of the 15 respondents, there were 8 men and 7 women.

The research instruments used include interview guidelines and document study guides. The interview guide includes open-ended questions to explore respondents' views and experiences about gender roles in organizations and factors that influence women's participation in leadership and committees. The document study guide contains a list of documents to be collected as secondary data, such as AD/ART (Articles of Association/Constitution and Bylaws), organizational structure, and activity reports from the past 5 years.

The following are some open interview questions that can be used to determine students' perceptions of gender equality:

1. What is your view on gender equality daily and in organizations such as student associations?
2. Are there any differences in treatment or opportunities between men and women in student organizations?
3. How does the organization provide equal opportunities for men and women in leadership and committees?
4. In your opinion, do gender stereotypes still affect women's participation in student organizations?
5. Are there any programs or initiatives from the organization to increase women's participation in student organizations?

Data can be collected through open interviews with selected respondents throughout January 2023. Document studies can be conducted by collecting organizational documents such as AD/ART, organizational structure, and activity reports from the past 5 years.

Interview data will be analysed using content analysis techniques to find important themes and relationships between them. Data from document studies can be analysed by comparing information in the documents and identifying patterns or trends that have emerged in recent years.

Conclusions can be drawn from the findings obtained from the data analysis. Recommendations can be made based on these findings, such as recommendations to increase women's participation in leadership

and committees, as well as efforts to eliminate gender stereotypes in organizational activities. Therefore, this qualitative research method can contribute to developing inclusive student organizations that embrace all individuals regardless of gender.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

The results of the study show that students understand the concept of gender equality theoretically, which is that equality is a condition in which men and women have equal rights and obligations. This understanding is also implemented in writing in the organizational rules (AD/ART), which do not mention anything related to differences in rights and obligations based on gender. However, the data shows that in the past 5 years, the proportion of male leadership has been more dominant than female leadership, with even the chairman always being held by males.

Furthermore, the study results show that men outnumber women and occupy positions with public roles in the organization, such as chairman, public relations department, sports department, and education department. This indicates that although gender equality is recognised in the organization, practices are still not in line with these values.

In addition, in some interviews with female students, there was a sense of inferiority where they felt it was normal for men to hold certain roles in the organization because it had always been that way. Attitudes like this can be one of the factors that affect women's participation in student organizations, and there needs to be action to increase awareness of the importance of gender equality in organizational activities.

From here, it can be understood that although students already understand the concept of gender equality theoretically and it has been implemented in organizational rules, there are still practices that make men more dominant in leadership and public roles in the organization. This needs to be a concern for the organization officials to strive to create inclusive organizational activities that embrace all individuals regardless of gender.

The gap between knowledge and reality in student organizations of Japanese language and literature in Medan

Gender equality is important in ensuring everyone has equal opportunities to develop their potential and contribute to society. Society is becoming increasingly aware of the importance of gender equality, including among students. Students are aware of the concept of gender and the importance of gender equality in everyday life, both in social and academic activities.

As evidence of students' commitment to gender equality, Hinode, Aotake, and Hikari student associations do not have written rules that discriminate based on gender. This reflects how these organizations strive to uphold the values of equality in their structure and organizational procedures. However, despite efforts to create an inclusive environment, challenges still need to be addressed in implementing gender equality in real life.

One of the challenges in implementing gender equality in student organizations of Japanese language and literature in Medan City is the gap between knowledge about gender equality and the reality in the organization. Although students understand the concept of gender equality theoretically, and these values have been implemented in organizational rules, practices still affect participation based on gender.

One example is the ability of Aotake students to explain the connection between gender phenomena in literary works, such as the portrayal of loneliness in Haruki Murakami's works. This knowledge demonstrates that students have a strong theoretical understanding of gender. However, this theoretical understanding does not necessarily translate into gender equality practices within the organization.

There are no restrictions on membership in the organization, and both men and women are free to occupy any position. Nevertheless, there are still differences in the roles of men and women in various organizational activities. For instance, men more often hold leadership positions and are responsible for public aspects of the organization, while women more often participate in domestic roles such as administration or cleanliness.

The realisation of gender equality in implementing organizational activities and committees among Japanese language and literature students has not been fully achieved. For example, in leadership roles, men have always been the organization's chairman for the past 5 years.

Hikari is the only association that has made a woman leader for one period, but this was due to the very small number of male students that year. This situation illustrates how men still dominate leadership positions, making it seem like the norm that is difficult to change.

Female students in domestic roles in organizations

During the interviews, the researchers tried to explore the reasons why women generally have more limited roles in organizations, while men tend to hold leadership positions and appear in public. Some interesting answers from female organization managers include the perception that it is already a norm, men are considered ideal leaders, have stronger physical abilities, and are not limited by time like women during activities or meetings.

From some interview quotes, other views were also revealed:

1. Regarding the chairman of the association, who is always male:
 - *Men are considered more free and quick in taking action.*
 - *Men are more responsive and easy to engage in activities, and it is easier for them to get permission from their parents to stay out late or stay overnight.*
2. Regarding the reasons why men or women must be in certain fields in a committee:
 - *Women are considered less capable in heavy physical work, such as lifting weights or driving.*
 - *Men and women are adjusted according to their abilities; for example, men do heavy physical work while women do lighter work.*
3. Regarding the view of women as the main leader:
 - *Most women are reluctant to become the main leader because they are more focused on their studies and have difficulty finding time for the organization.*
 - *Some women feel unable to manage their friends, especially men.*
 - *Women are considered less able to lead because they tend to be too emotional.*

One interesting response from a respondent was when asked, "What do you think if the main leader is a woman?" and the answer was

", It is not suitable and does not fit with the cultural principles and religion in Indonesia. Especially in Japanese culture, which historically tends to make men leaders."

Additional comments from the respondent indicate that some individual students have more conservative views about women as the main leader. They feel that women as leaders are not in line with cultural and religious principles in Indonesia and refer to Japanese cultural history, which tends to make men leaders.

Teaching in college is important in shaping perceptions of gender equality among students. Lectures that convey information about gender equality, human rights, and inclusive perspectives can help students better understand gender issues and the importance of creating an equal environment for all members of society.

However, if teaching in college is not enough to convey the values of gender equality or even indirectly supports existing stereotypes and social norms, it can affect students' perceptions and reinforce views related to gender inequality.

From these answers, gender perceptions in organizations are still heavily influenced by stereotypes and social norms. It is necessary for the reasons behind these perceptions to be delved deeper into and understood so that an inclusive and balanced environment can be created in the future and gender equality can be promoted in every aspect of organizational activities.

Habits that instil inferiority

There is a theory of inferiority by Alfred Adler that explains that the feeling of inferiority is the main motivation in human behaviour, and individuals seek ways to overcome this feeling. According to Adler, individuals try to compensate for this feeling of inferiority through efforts to become superior or succeed in various areas of life.

Based on respondents' answers regarding women's physical limitations, it appears that women may feel inferior in the physical context compared to men. They believe men have stronger physical abilities and are more suitable for heavy physical work, while women are deemed more suitable for lighter work. This opinion may have influenced women's perceptions of their abilities, causing them to feel incapable of performing tasks deemed suitable for men.

In the context of Adler's theory, women may try to compensate for this feeling of inferiority by focusing on activities that are considered more appropriate or socially acceptable, such as managing consumption, typing files, recording meeting results, making reports, decorating, and cleaning. However, this approach can reinforce existing gender stereotypes and maintain an imbalanced division of roles between men and women.

This phenomenon has been going on for quite some time and has become cultural, causing feelings of inferiority among female members of every Japanese language and literature student organization in Medan. The role imbalance in male-dominated organizations makes women feel less capable of filling leadership positions or public roles. This is closely related to stereotypes and social norms that still exist in society.

The perception that women are more suitable in domestic or administrative roles, while men are more suitable for leadership positions and physical tasks, creates limitations for women in developing their potential. In addition, this feeling of inferiority can also affect women's self-confidence in pursuing positions similar to men in organizations.

To overcome this feeling of inferiority, women must recognise and appreciate their abilities and encourage gender empowerment and equality within organizations. In addition, there needs to be an effort to change societal views about gender roles and eliminate stereotypes that limit women from various opportunities and responsibilities that should be accessible to all individuals, regardless of gender.

CONCLUSION

From the research and interviews conducted, it was revealed that although students understand the concept of gender equality theoretically and apply it in organizational rules, existing practices still show an imbalance between men and women. Men dominate leadership positions and public roles in organizations, while women are more involved in domestic roles.

Gender perceptions influenced by stereotypes and social norms also contribute to feelings of inferiority among women, who may try to compensate for these feelings by focusing on suitable activities. This results in an imbalanced division of roles between men and women in organizations.

In conclusion, organization leaders and members of society need to increase awareness about the importance of gender equality and strive for an inclusive environment that embraces all individuals regardless of gender. Efforts are being made to change views about gender roles, empower women, and eliminate stereotypes that limit individual potential based on gender. By doing so, organizations will be able to be created that truly embody the values of gender equality and provide equal opportunities for all members.

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